

Physical, Textural and Sensory Properties of Noodles Supplemented with Tilapia Bone Flour (*Tilapia nilotica*)

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Abstract : Fishbone of Nile tilapia (*Tilapia nilotica*), waste from the frozen Nile tilapia fillet factory, is one of calcium sources. In order to increase fish bone powder value, this study aimed to investigate the effect of tilapia bone flour (TBF) addition (5, 10, 15% by flour weight) on cooking quality, texture and sensory attributes of noodles. The results indicated that tensile strength, color value (a^*) and water absorption of noodles significantly decreased ($p \leq 0.05$) as the levels of TBF increased from 0-15%. While cooking loss, cooking time and color values (L^* and b^*) of noodles significantly increased ($p \leq 0.05$). Sensory evaluation indicated that noodles with 5% TBF received the highest overall acceptability score.

Keywords : tilapia bone flour, noodles, cooking quality, calcium

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